

Photophysical and protolytic properties of neutral red with macrocyclic receptors: Fluorescence sensor and drug delivery applications

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Stimuli-responsive supramolecular assemblies of potential drug/guest molecules through non-covalent host-guest interaction have gained enormous interest as they find promising in drug delivery and fluorescence sensor applications. In this review article, the supramolecular interactions of a biologically important intracellular pH indicator dye Neutral Red (NR) with three macrocyclic hosts, namely, cucurbit[7]uril (CB7), *p*-sulfonatocalix[6]arene (SCX6) and β -cyclodextrin (β -CD), having comparable cavity dimensions, have been discussed. The protonated form of neutral red interacts strongly with CB7 and SCX6 cation receptors (10^5 – 10^6 M⁻¹), whereas the neutral form interacts with β -CD. As a result, NR displays upward pK_a shift (2–2.3 units) in the presence of CB7 or SCX6 and downward pK_a shift (0.7 unit) with β -CD. The binding affinity of NR with CB7/SCX6 can be fine-tuned by addition and competitive binding of metal ions, which leads to a pK_a shift of the dye. This pK_a shift method has been exploited to relocate the dye from the macrocyclic cavity of CB7 to the biomolecular pocket of bovine serum albumin which can find applications in drug delivery. The fluorescence quenching observed in the SCX-neutral red interactions stands in contrast to the fluorescence enhancement observed with CB7 and β -CD. This is due to the unique portal stacking interaction of NRH⁺ with the SCXs, compared to the axial inclusion geometry documented for CB7 and β -CD. The electron transfer from the SCX to the neutral red dye is adjudged to be the effective excited-state relaxation pathway leading to fluorescence quenching. In combination with the metal-ion induced fluorescence regeneration, the SCX-neutral red system finds potential applications in drug delivery, photodynamic therapy, catalysis, and sensor applications.

Keywords: Host-guest chemistry, neutral red, cucurbiturils, calixarenes, cyclodextrins, photophysical properties.

Introduction

Modulation of molecular properties through the complexation of fluorescent dyes by macrocyclic hosts is an area of enormous research interest in supramolecular chemistry^{1–4}. By extending several non-covalent interactions such as hydrogen bonding, dipole-dipole and ion-dipole interactions and hydrophobic interactions, such as van der Waals, π - π interactions towards the encapsulated guests, macrocyclic hosts can alter their photophysical characteristics^{5,6}, most prominently, enhance their fluorescence quantum yield or photostability through complexation which find potential applications in photonic devices, optical sensors, *on-off* switches, aqueous dye laser, and drug delivery^{7–15}. Furthermore,

the non-covalent binding interactions in host-guest complexes are mainly weak and reversible in nature which makes it suitable to tune these complexes in a controlled manner by using a range of external stimuli like competitive binders, pH, temperature, light, redox control, etc.^{11,16–18}.

Cyclodextrins (CDs; Chart 1), a family of the classical cyclic oligosaccharides, consist of (α -1,4)-linked α -D-glucopyranose units and contain a significantly hydrophobic central cavity and a hydrophilic outer surface^{19–22}. Due to the chair conformation of the glucopyranose units, cyclodextrins are shaped like a truncated cone. The central cavity is lined by the skeletal carbons and ethereal oxygens of the glucose residues, which gives it a hydrophobic

character and is instrumental for binding nonpolar alkyl and aryl residues. The hydroxyl groups are orientated to the cone exterior with the primary hydroxyl groups of the sugar residues at the narrow edge of the cone and the secondary hydroxyl groups at the wider edge. This arrangement provides additional hydrogen bonding sites for the binding of organic guests, particularly anionic guest molecules. The natural α -, β - and γ -cyclodextrins consist of six, seven, and eight glucopyranose units, respectively^{19,21–24}. CDs are the first receptor molecules whose binding properties towards organic molecules have been recognized and extensively investigated, yielding a wealth of results on physical and chemical features of molecular complexation. The binding constants of CD-based host-guest complexes range typically from 10 to 10^5 M^{-1} , which requires millimolar concentrations of the macrocycle in order to achieve significant complexation of the guest molecules in aqueous solution^{19,21}.

The cyclo-oligomeric phenols known as calix[n]arenes (CX n) have received much interest as basic molecular scaffolds for the construction of selective ionophores/ion sensors^{24–26}. The name ‘calixarene’ was coined by C. David Gutsche because of the resemblance of the bowl-shaped conformation of the smaller calixarenes to a Greek vase²⁷. Although numerous differently functionalized water-soluble calixarenes are known, the sulfonated analogues (SCX), introduced by Shinkai *et al.*, are the most prominent water-soluble calixarenes having many potential applications such as enzyme mimetics, antiviral, antibacterial, enzyme blocking, and inhibi-

tion and disintegration of amyloid fibrils, ion sensitive electrodes or sensors, selective membranes and non-linear optics^{25,28–31}. These container molecules are composed of *p*-hydroxybenzenesulfonate units linked by methylene groups (Chart 1), forming π -electron rich and flexible macrocycles, which have shown extensive use as receptors for cations, anions and neutral molecules^{25,26}. Depending on the number of *p*-hydroxybenzenesulfonate units, homologues of different sizes are known, prominently, *p*-sulfonatocalix[4]arene (SCX4), *p*-sulfonatocalix[6]arene (SCX6) and *p*-sulfonatocalix[8]arene (SCX8). All SCXs have cone-shaped structures with two unsymmetrical hydrophilic portal ends and an interior hydrophobic cavity, akin to cyclodextrins (CD)^{2,29,32}.

Cucurbit[n]urils (CB n) are a relatively young class of macrocyclic receptor molecules composed of methylene-bridged glycoluril monomers having highly symmetrical hydrophobic cavities accessible through two identical, negatively polarized carbonyl laced portals^{1–4,33–35}. Depending on the number of glycoluril units, homologues of different sizes are known, prominently CB5, CB6, CB7, CB8 and CB10. In recent years, CBs have been established as versatile and interesting host molecules, which form stable inclusion complexes with small guest molecules such as organic dyes, metal cations, and protonated alkyl and arylamines, amino acids^{1–4,17,18,34,36} and exclusion complexes with polyanions such as polyoxometalates³⁷. Among the set of CBs, the complexation behavior of cucurbit[7]uril (CB7, Chart 1), has been extensively studied due to its appropriate cavity size and portal diameter comparable to the

Chart 1. Representative chemical structures of three different classes of macrocyclic receptors.

dimension (width) of most small size organic guests and also due to its substantial solubility in water as compared to the other homologues like CB5, CB6, CB8 and CB10¹⁻⁴. The water solubility of the CB n can be enhanced in the presence of salts, at low pH, or in the presence of charged guests³⁴. All cucurbituril homologues, except CB5, can form much stronger host/guest complexes than cyclodextrins and their binding constants range typically from 10⁴ to 10¹⁵ M⁻¹. We have explored the complexation behaviour of variety of fluorescent dyes with CBs since we expected fundamentally different photophysical and chemical behaviour from two perspectives: First, dye molecules immersed in the cavity of CBs experience an exceptionally low polarizability (close to the gas phase), which is expected to decrease the radiative decay rate constants, and second, CBs act as cation receptors and should have stronger interactions with cationic fluorescent dyes².

In this review article, we have compared the changes in the photophysical properties and the changes in its protolytic equilibria (pK_a shift) of a biologically relevant dye, neutral red, in the presence of CB7, SCX6 and β -CD having similar cavity dimension (~ 7.6 Å for SCX6, 6–7 Å for β -CD and 7.3 Å for CB7)²⁹. In addition, all three host molecules are moderately water-soluble (~ 100 mM for SCX, ~ 16 mM for β -CD and ~ 5 mM for CB7)²⁹ and they display differential affinity towards the protonated or deprotonated forms of a guest, which can guide to a supramolecular control over the prototropic equilibria of the guest molecule^{32,38,39}. Metal ion-induced pK_a tuning in NR-CB7/SCX systems^{1,11,32} and consequently, the relocation of NR from CB7 cavity into the hydrophobic pockets of bovine serum albumin (BSA) have also been discussed.

The fluorescent dye, neutral red (3-amino-7-(dimethylamino)-2-methyl phenazine), has been extensively used as a fluorescent probe and stain for biological systems³⁹. Importantly, the pK_a value of neutral red lies in the physiologically most relevant region (6.8)^{38,39}. Depending upon the pH of the solution, neutral red exists in two prototropic forms,

one being neutral (NR) and the other one being protonated (NRH⁺, nitrogen atom at 5-position of the phenazine ring is being protonated, *cf.* Chart 2); the latter form is red and dominates in most biological applications, which accounts for the trivial name of this dye³⁸. This has enabled numerous biological applications as a pH indicator, because the dye shows characteristic colour and fluorescence changes with pH, and has led to related applications in investigations of microheterogeneous and confined media such as micelles, microemulsions, cyclodextrins, cucurbiturils and calixarenes^{32,38,39}. Specifically, the interaction of neutral red with macrocyclic hosts such as β -CD and CB7 shows enhanced fluorescence intensity and contrasting shift in the protolytic equilibrium of the dye to a large extent^{38,39}, whereas the fluorescence intensity of neutral red is largely quenched in the presence of SCX6³². Thus, macrocyclic hosts can improve the photophysical characteristics of dyes, enhance/diminish their fluorescence quantum yields or improve photostability and can display a deaggregating effect and thereby improve water solubility. However, these effects are found to be specific with host, guest and pH and it is worthwhile to document such interesting photophysical and protolytic changes in neutral red dye with the three hosts presented here.

Chart 2. Chemical structures of protonated (NRH⁺) and neutral (NR) forms of neutral red dye.

Absorption and fluorescence spectral characteristics of neutral red with CB7

The ground-state pK_a value of neutral red in water has been estimated as 6.5 ± 0.3 , which is in good agreement with the reported value of 6.8^{38,39}. Therefore, in acidic aqueous solution, the protonated form of the dye (NRH⁺) prevails, which has its absorption maximum at 535 nm; in alkaline media, the neutral form dominates with an absorption maximum

at 450 nm^{38,39}.

Upon addition of CB7 (150 μM) to an aqueous solution of neutral red at pH 2 (NRH⁺ form), the absorbance decreased slightly and the absorption peak showed a hypsochromic shift, from 535 nm to 529 nm, with an apparent isosbestic point at 520 nm (insets of Fig. 1A)³⁸. Interestingly, these spectral changes occurred already at few micromolar (μM) concentrations of CB7 and became effectively saturated at 20 μM , suggesting a very strong binding of the cationic NRH⁺ form of the dye. In contrast, upon addition of CB7 to an aqueous solution of neutral red at pH 11 (NR form), the absorption peak showed a gradual increase in absorbance with increasing CB7 content and a bathochromic shift from 450 nm to 467 nm, with an isosbestic point at ~ 450 nm (insets of Fig. 1B)³⁸. These changes, however, took place with substantially higher CB7 concentration (~ 150 μM), which implies a weaker binding of the neutral NR form³⁸. However, the stoichiometry calculation using Job's plot indicates that 1:1 inclusion complex formation between the dye and CB7.

Both the protolytic forms of neutral red (NRH⁺/NR) display fluorescence bands in the 500–800 nm region with an emission maximum at ~ 639 nm for

NRH⁺ (pH ~ 5) and ~ 633 nm for NR (pH ~ 10). The fluorescence characteristics of both NR and NRH⁺ forms of the dye showed dramatic changes upon addition of CB7, namely a blue shift by 20–25 nm and a sharp increase in fluorescence intensity (Figs. 1A and B). In the presence of 150 μM CB7, for example, the increase in fluorescence quantum yield (ϕ_f) for the NRH⁺ and NR forms was 5-fold and 6-fold, respectively³⁸. The increased fluorescence intensities are commonly attributed to the altered (less polar) microenvironment inside the macrocyclic host cavities and/or to a spatial confinement effect, which limits alternative deactivation pathways³⁸. For neutral red, vibrational and rotational motions of the N(CH₃)₂ group of the dye are expected to be strongly coupled to the nonradiative de-excitation channel of the excited molecule, and a restriction of the motions of this group by confinement may be particularly effective in preventing radiationless deactivation. In the case of CB7, the exceptional chemical inertness of the host molecule and the low polarizability inside the cavity need also to be taken into account and may contribute to the fluorescence enhancement^{5,6}. The dramatic fluorescence enhancement provides strong evidence that inclusion complexes are indeed formed. At the same time, neutral red showed emission quenching in the presence of higher homologue of CB7 i.e. cucurbit[8]uril (CB8)

Fig. 1. (A) Steady-state fluorescence and ground-state absorption (inset) spectra of NRH⁺ (2.07×10^{-6} M) in aqueous solution at pH 2 at different concentrations of CB7. [CB7]/ μM : (1) 0.0, (2) 0.8, (3) 1.5, (4) 3.9, (5) 14.0 and (6) 44.0. (B) Steady-state fluorescence spectra and ground-state absorption (inset) of NR (3.8×10^{-6} M) in aqueous solution at pH ~ 11 at different concentrations of CB7. [CB7]/ μM : (1) 0, (2) 14, (3) 35, (4) 50, (5) 75, (6) 112 and (7) 150. Reprinted with permission from Ref. 38. Copyright (2006) American Chemical Society.

due to its dimer formation within the host cavity¹³.

NR shows dual solvatochromism and can emit either from a locally excited (LE) state or from the twisted intramolecular charge transfer (TICT) state, depending on the polarity of the medium; the TICT state of NR participates only in high polarity solvents^{39–41}. In the present case, the emission for the NR•CB7 complex can be assigned to the LE state of the dye, which is consistent with the expectedly lower polarity and hydrophobicity inside the cucurbituril cavity³⁸. For NRH⁺, TICT state formation is not possible such that the fluorescence of the NRH⁺ form, also in its CB7 complex, can be assigned to the LE state as well.

The binding constant values (*K*) obtained from the nonlinear fittings of the experimental data using 1:1 model were $(6.0 \pm 1.0) \times 10^5 \text{ M}^{-1}$ for the NRH⁺•CB7 complex and $(6.5 \pm 1.0) \times 10^3 \text{ M}^{-1}$ for the NR•CB7 complex. Accordingly, the protonated form of neutral red binds more than 2 orders of magnitude stronger to CB7, but the binding of the neutral form with CB7 is also sizable. The increased binding of the protonated form can be readily rationalized by recalling that CBs have cation receptor properties, since their carbonyl rims can stabilize positive charges through ion-dipole interactions³⁸.

Effect of CB7 complexation on the acidity constant of the dye

Significant changes in the protolytic equilibrium of the included guests are often encountered in the host-guest interactions due to the preferential binding of the prototropic forms with the host. The advantages of such pK_a shifts are enormous and have been evaluated for various applications^{1,29,38}. Upward pK_a shifts are usually observed for weakly basic molecules in the presence of cation-receptor or hydrogen bond-acceptor hosts, while downward pK_a shifts are expected for anion-receptor, hydrogen bond donor host molecules or those offering a nonpolar cavity²⁹. In tune with the active contribution from different research groups^{7,29,42–44}, we have reported independently the supramolecular pK_a shifts, of sev-

eral guest molecules such as neutral red, acridine orange, hydroxyphenylbenzimidazole, hoechst-33258, coumarin 6 and acridine by using host molecules such as cyclodextrins, cucurbiturils and calixarenes^{1,24,26,32,38,45–50}.

In the intermediary pH range around the pK_a value of neutral red, the prototropic equilibrium between NRH⁺ and NR in the presence of CB7 should follow the four-state model in Scheme 1. Accordingly, complexation of the protonated and the neutral form, as well as protonation of the uncomplexed and complexed neutral forms need to be considered and a thermodynamic cycle (eq. (2)) applies³⁸. From this, the pK_a value of the dye•CB7 complex has been calculated from the independently determined binding constants for the neutral and protonated form and the known pK_a value of the uncomplexed dye. A pK_a' value of *ca.* 8.7 results, suggesting an exceptionally large pK_a shift by ~ 2 units³⁸. This means that neutral red, once complexed by CB7, becomes a *ca.* 100 times stronger base than in its free form, with the ion-dipole interactions offered by the CB7 macrocycle providing the additional driving force for complexation³⁸.

$$K_a' = K_a K_{eq}(\text{NR}) / K_{eq}(\text{NRH}^+) \quad (2)$$

Scheme 1. Four state model.

The spectrophotometric titrations of neutral red in the absence and presence of 150 μM CB7 with pH (Fig. 2) have been carried out. The corresponding titrations (changes in the absorbance at 530 nm) revealed the previously documented⁴¹ pK_a value around 6.8 for the free dye, but the pK_a' value of the complexed dye shifted by *ca.* 2 units to a value of 8.8 ± 0.1 , applying a simple titration fit. This is in excellent agreement with the value projected from the relative binding constants.

Fig. 2. Absorption spectra of neutral red (2.9×10^{-6} M) in water containing 150 μ M CB7 at different pH: (1) 3.54, (2) 4.20, (3) 5.76, (4) 7.26, (5) 7.85, (6) 8.33, (7) 8.82, (8) 9.24, (9) 9.66 and (10) 11.0. The inset shows the variation in absorbance with pH at 530 nm in the absence and presence of 150 μ M CB7. Reprinted with permission from Ref. 38. Copyright (2006) American Chemical Society.

Absorption and fluorescence spectral characteristics of neutral red with SCX6

The absorbance of neutral red ($\sim 2.6 \mu\text{M}$) at pH ~ 5 (NRH^+ form) decreased and the spectral maximum showed a blue shift, from 535 nm to 528 nm upto the addition of $\sim 5 \mu\text{M}$ of SCX6 as shown in Fig. 3A. Further addition of SCX6 led to the shift in the absorption peak to 525 nm with slight increase in the absorbance and saturated at $\sim 40 \mu\text{M}$ of SCX6

(Fig. 3A), suggesting a very strong interaction of the cationic NRH^+ form of the dye with the SCX6³². The stoichiometric analysis by the Job plot (inset of Fig. 3A) displayed a maximum in the absorbance changes at 0.5 mole fractions which corresponds to a 1:1 inclusion complex formation between SCX6 and NRH^+ at pH ~ 5 . In contrast, upon addition of SCX6 to an aqueous solution of neutral red at pH ~ 10 (NR form), the absorption profile displayed only a nominal decrease in the absorbance with increasing SCX6 upto 1.5 mM (Fig. 3B), which implies a weaker interaction of the neutral NR form with SCX6³².

Fluorescence titrations were performed for the quantification of the host-guest interactions of neutral red with SCX6 in terms of binding constants. The fluorescence intensity of NRH^+ decreased substantially in the presence of SCX6 along with slight hypsochromic shift in the spectral maximum as shown in Fig. 4A. Saturation in the fluorescence intensity was attained with $\sim 40 \mu\text{M}$ of SCX6, indicating strong interaction between them. However, the NR form at pH ~ 10 showed only a nominal quenching in the fluorescence intensity and saturated at very high concentration (~ 1.5 mM) of SCX6. These results clearly suggest that SCX6 has more affinity for NRH^+ than the NR form of the dye³². Unlike

Fig. 3. (A) Absorption spectra of NRH^+ ($\sim 2.6 \mu\text{M}$, pH ~ 5) with increasing concentration of SCX6 (μM): (1) 0.0, (2) 1.0, (3) 2.5, (4) 5.0, (5) 10.0, (6) 20.0 and (7) 39.0. (B) Absorption spectra of NR ($\sim 5 \mu\text{M}$, pH ~ 10) with increasing concentration of SCX6 (μM): (1) 0, (2) 10, (3) 30, (4) 77, (5) 122, (6) 180, (7) 627 and (8) 1500. Inset shows the Job plot evaluated by the absorbance changes at 535 nm for the SCX6: NRH^+ complex. n_{NRH^+} represents the mole fraction of NRH^+ . Reproduced from Ref. 32 by permission of The Royal Society of Chemistry.

Fig. 4. (A) Emission spectra of NRH^+ ($\sim 2.6 \mu\text{M}$, $\text{pH} \sim 5$) with increasing concentration of SCX6 (μM): (1) 0.0, (2) 1.0, (3) 2.5, (4) 5.0, (5) 10.0, (6) 20.0, (7) 39.0 and (8) 77.0. (B) Emission spectra of NR ($\sim 5 \mu\text{M}$, $\text{pH} \sim 10$) with increasing concentration of SCX6 (μM): (1) 0, (2) 10, (3) 30, (4) 77, (5) 122, (6) 627 and (7) 1500. Insets show the fluorescence titration curves (ΔI_{fl} versus $[\text{SCX6}]$) plot for the respective protonated and neutral form complexes. Circles represent the experimental data points and solid lines are the fitted curve. Reproduced from Ref. 32 by permission of The Royal Society of Chemistry.

$\text{NRH}^+ \cdot \text{CB7}$ complex, the severe fluorescence quenching observed in case of 1:1 inclusion complex formation between neutral red and SCX6 is intriguing. The Stern-Volmer plot for this quenching interaction displayed a steep slope in the initial concentration of SCX indicating the presence of strong static quenching due to ground state complex formation. The quenching of fluorescence suggests that there is an additional mode of excited-state relaxation for the dye in the $\text{NRH}^+ \cdot \text{SCX6}$ complex and $\text{NR} \cdot \text{SCX6}$ complex, compared to that of free dye in water. Since the calixarenes are known to be good electron donors^{25,26,32,51,52} and the excited state of phenazine dye is potentially good electron acceptor⁵³, electron transfer from the phenolate groups of SCX6 to the NRH^+ and NR acceptors is a quite probable mechanism resulting an effective way of excited-state relaxation.

The binding constants (K) for the NRH^+ and NR forms of neutral red dye with SCX6 host were estimated at suitable pH conditions by the fluorescence titration method using 1:1 binding model. From the plot of emission intensity (at 637 nm for NRH^+ and 630 nm for NR) with SCX6 (insets of Fig. 4), the binding constants were estimated as $(8.6 \pm 0.9) \times 10^5 \text{ M}^{-1}$ for the $\text{NRH}^+ \cdot \text{SCX6}$ complex and $(4.8 \pm 0.5) \times 10^3 \text{ M}^{-1}$ for the complex. According to

these values, the protonated form of the dye binds ~ 2 orders of magnitude stronger to SCX6, compared to the binding of the neutral form (NR) with SCX6³².

Effect of SCX6 complexation on the acidity constant of neutral red

Considering the substantial complexation of both the NRH^+ and NR forms with SCX6 host, the $\text{p}K_a'$ value of $\text{SCX6} \cdot \text{NR}$ complex has been calculated from the independently determined binding constants for the neutral and protonated forms and the known $\text{p}K_a$ value of the uncomplexed dye using eq. (2)³². By this method we arrived at a $\text{p}K_a$ value of ~ 8.75 which is ~ 2.25 units higher than the $\text{p}K_a$ value of the uncomplexed neutral red dye. In other words, neutral red dye, once complexed with SCX6, becomes *ca.* > 170 times stronger base than in its free form. To obtain a more confirmative experimental value of the $\text{p}K_a$ shift, we have carried out spectrophotometric pH titrations of neutral red both in the absence and presence of 1 mM SCX6, with changing the solution pH and the spectral changes are shown in Fig. 5A. The spectral changes display an apparent isosbestic point at around 480 nm, which is not sharp as expected for four-state model (Scheme 1)³⁸. From this, the OD changes at 540 nm have been plotted versus pH and the $\text{p}K_a$ curves for the dye in the

absence and presence of SCX6 has been plotted (Fig. 5B)³².

Following the Scheme 1, the pH-dependent absorbance of the dye at any particular wavelength can be expressed as^{32,45}:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{OD} = & \frac{\text{OD}_{\text{NRH}^+}^\infty}{(1 + 10^{\text{pH}-\text{p}K_a} + 10^{\text{pH}-\text{p}K_a} K_{\text{eq}}^1[\text{SCX6}]_0 + K_{\text{eq}}^2[\text{SCX6}]_0)} \\
 & + \frac{\text{OD}_{\text{NR}}^\infty}{(1 + 10^{\text{p}K_a-\text{pH}} + 10^{\text{p}K_a-\text{pH}} K_{\text{eq}}^2[\text{SCX6}]_0 + K_{\text{eq}}^1[\text{SCX6}]_0)} \\
 & + \frac{\text{OD}_{\text{SCX6 NRH}^+}^\infty}{(1 + 10^{\text{pH}-\text{p}K_a} + 10^{\text{pH}-\text{p}K_a} \frac{1}{K_{\text{eq}}^1[\text{SCX6}]_0} + \frac{1}{K_{\text{eq}}^2[\text{SCX6}]_0})} \\
 & + \frac{\text{OD}_{\text{SCX6 NR}}^\infty}{(1 + 10^{\text{p}K_a-\text{pH}} + 10^{\text{p}K_a-\text{pH}} \frac{1}{K_{\text{eq}}^2[\text{SCX6}]_0} + \frac{1}{K_{\text{eq}}^1[\text{SCX6}]_0})} \quad (3)
 \end{aligned}$$

where $\text{OD}_{\text{NRH}^+}^\infty$, $\text{OD}_{\text{NR}}^\infty$, $\text{OD}_{\text{SCX6 NRH}^+}^\infty$ and $\text{OD}_{\text{SCX6 NR}}^\infty$ are the extrapolated absorbance of the NRH^+ , NR, $\text{SCX6}\cdot\text{NRH}^+$ or $\text{SCX6}\cdot\text{NR}$ forms, respectively. Fitting of the data in Fig. 5B(c) according to eq. (3) and substituting $\text{p}K_a = 6.5$, $K_{\text{eq}}^1 = 8.6 \times 10^5 \text{ M}^{-1}$ and $K_{\text{eq}}^2 = 4.8 \times 10^3 \text{ M}^{-1}$, the $\text{p}K_a'$ value thus estimated for the $\text{SCX6}\cdot\text{NR}$ complex is 8.8 ± 0.1 . This $\text{p}K_a'$ value is substantially higher (upward shift by

ca. 2.3 units) than the $\text{p}K_a$ value of the free dye in aqueous solution and is in excellent agreement with the value projected from the four-state model (Scheme 1) using relative binding constants according to eq. (2). In this system also, it is observed that the cationic form of the dye (NRH^+) preferentially binds to SCX6 to form the inclusion complex, whereas its neutral form, NR, exhibits weak interaction towards SCX6. Therefore, an increment in the $\text{p}K_a$ value of NRH^+ from ~ 6.5 to ~ 8.8 in the presence of SCX6 is in line with the stabilization of the NRH^+ form by the SCX6 cavity³².

To generalize the supramolecular $\text{p}K_a$ shift in neutral red amongst the homologous host of *p*-sulfonatocalix[*n*]arenes, the fluorescence titration and pH-titration experiments of neutral red with *p*-sulfonatocalix[4]arene (SCX4) have been carried out. In this case also it is seen that the fluorescence intensity of both the forms of neutral red get quenched with SCX4 addition, though the extent of quenching is more in case of NRH^+ form than the NR form. Similar to $\text{SCX6}\cdot\text{NRH}^+$ complex, NRH^+ forms 1:1 complex with SCX4 and gets stacked at the $-\text{SO}_3^-$ portal of SCX4 as shown in Fig. 6B. The pH dependent titration of neutral red in the presence of 1 mM SCX4 and the plot of OD changes at 540 nm versus pH revealed a $\text{p}K_a$ shift of about 2 units i.e. from 6.5 for free dye to 8.5 for $\text{SCX4}\cdot\text{NR}$ complex³².

Fig. 5. (A) Absorption spectra of neutral red ($3.5 \times 10^{-6} \text{ M}$) in water containing 1 mM SCX6 at different pH: (1) 3.8, (2) 4.5, (3) 5.0, (4) 5.5, (5) 6.5, (6) 7.0, (7) 7.5, (8) 8.0, (9) 8.5, (10) 8.7, (11) 9.0, (12) 10.0, (13) 10.5 and (14) 11.0. (B) The variation in absorbance with pH at 540 nm in the absence (a) and presence of 1 mM SCX4 (b) and 1 mM of SCX6 (c). Reproduced from Ref. 32 by permission of The Royal Society of Chemistry.

Absorption and fluorescence spectral characteristics of neutral red with β -CD

The absorption spectrum of NR displayed a marginal blue shift along with a gradual reduction in the peak absorbance in the presence of β -CD at pH ~ 9 . As shown in Fig. 6A, the absorbance at the longest wavelength absorption maxima (~ 452 nm) of NR with the increasing concentration of β -CD at pH ~ 9 initially decreases and then attends a limiting value at a β -CD concentration of ≥ 5 mM, indicating almost complete complexation of NR with β -CD³⁹. The absorption maxima ($\lambda_{\text{abs}}^{\text{max}}$) showed a blue shift of ~ 8 nm in the presence of 10 mM concentration of β -CD. It has also been observed that while the absorbance of NR in the 450 nm region reduces with increasing concentration of β -CD, a small increase in absorbance was seen in the 350-nm region. At pH ~ 4 , where neutral red exists in its cationic form (NRH⁺), the absorption spectra did not show any change even in the presence of the highest concentration of β -CD used (10 mM), indicating that NRH⁺ does not form an inclusion complex with β -CD³⁹.

The fluorescence characteristics of NR in aqueous solutions at pH ~ 9 exhibited drastic changes in the presence of β -CD. The fluorescence spectra underwent a gradual blue shift on increasing the β -CD

concentration. In the presence of ~ 10 mM β -CD, the fluorescence peak of NR ($\lambda_{\text{em}}^{\text{max}} \sim 588$ nm) was blue shifted by ~ 37 nm as compared to that observed in the absence of β -CD ($\lambda_{\text{em}}^{\text{max}} \sim 625$ nm)³⁹. The fluorescence intensity of NR is also seen to increase substantially in the presence of β -CD (Fig. 6B)³⁹. Fig. 6B shows the effect of increasing β -CD concentration on the fluorescence spectra of NR and the inset of Fig. 6 shows the double reciprocal plot of $1/(I_f - I_f^0)$ vs $1/[\text{CD}]_0$. From the slope and intercept of the inset, the binding constant value for a 1:1 binding has been estimated to be 490 M^{-1} . Since, the plot deviates from linearity at higher β -CD concentration, it may indicate the simultaneous formation of 1:1 and 2:1 complexes between β -CD and NR in aqueous medium and the association constants K_1 and K_2 were estimated as 411 ± 25 and $420 \pm 25 \text{ M}^{-1}$, respectively³⁹.

Effect of β -CD complexation on the acidity constant of neutral red

The effect of β -CD on the protolytic equilibrium between NRH⁺ and NR has been investigated by following the pH-dependent changes in the absorption spectra of the dye in aqueous solution containing β -CD and are shown in Fig. 7³⁹. Following pH-dependent changes in the absorbance at 535 nm (in-

Fig. 6. (A) Absorption spectra of NR ($1.17 \times 10^{-5} \text{ M}$) in aqueous solutions containing varying concentrations of β -CD at pH ~ 9 . Concentrations of β -CD: (a) 0, (b) 0.2, (c) 0.7, (d) 1.0, (e) 2.0, (f) 5.0, (g) 7.0 and (h) 10 mM. (B) Fluorescence spectra of aqueous NR ($1.17 \times 10^{-5} \text{ M}$) at pH ~ 9 containing (1) 0, (2) 0.2, (3) 0.5, (4) 0.7, (5) 1.0, (6) 2.0, (7) 5.0, (8) 7.0 and (9) 10 mM β -CD. Inset: Double reciprocal plot of NR/ β -CD complex, $1/(I_f - I_f^0)$ vs $1/[\text{CD}]_0$. Reprinted with permission from Ref. 39. Copyright (2004) American Chemical Society.

set of Fig. 7), the ground state pK_a of the dye in the presence of β -CD (10 mM) has been determined to be 6.06 ± 0.05 , which is much lower than the value of 6.81 ± 0.05 measured in the absence of β -CD³⁹. The NR form of the dye forms inclusion complex with β -CD, whereas, its cationic form, NRH^+ , does not interact with β -CD. The complexation of NR with β -CD causes prototropic equilibrium (eq. (1)) to shift in the forward direction. Therefore, a lowering in the pK_a value of NRH^+ in the presence of β -CD is observed. To correlate pK_a changes with the nature of complex formed (1:1 or 1:2) measurements are performed at varying β -CD concentrations. The measured pK_a values do not show significant variation in the selected β -CD concentration range, 1 mM (6.1 ± 0.04), 2 mM (6.0 ± 0.05), and 5 mM (6.05 ± 0.04), respectively³⁹. These results clearly indicate that the changes in pK_a are associated with 1:1 complex and the preferential binding of the NR, which affects the protolytic equilibrium. The successive binding of the 1:1 complex by a second β -CD does not have any impact on pK_a .

Fig. 7. Absorption spectra of neutral red (1×10^{-5} M) in water containing 10 mM β -CD at different pHs. (1) 3.56, (2) 4.53, (3) 5.2, (4) 5.8, (5) 6.07, (6) 6.5, (7) 6.74, (8) 7.15, (9) 7.52, (10) 8.07, (11) 8.83, and (12) 9.78. Inset: Variation in absorbance with pH at 535 nm. Reprinted with permission from Ref. 39. Copyright (2004) American Chemical Society.

Geometry optimization

From all the above data it is evident that the NRH^+ dye experiences strong modulation on the excited state dynamics when bound to the cavity of the host

molecules. To assert the host-guest geometrical arrangement, PM3/MM level energy optimization calculations were performed. The optimized structures thus calculated are presented in Fig. 8³². It is seen that the NRH^+ stacks flat on the $-\text{SO}_3^-$ portal giving maximum interaction. All attempt to optimize a vertically included NRH^+ in the SCX6/SCX4 host ended up in the portal stacked complex only³². The ΔH_f of the 1:1 exclusion complex formation as estimated at this level of theory is 260 kcal/mol with SCX6• NRH^+ and -223 kcal/mol with SCX4• NRH^+ , whereas, with CB7 and β -CD, the dye shows axial binding³². The ΔH_f of the 1:1 inclusion complex formation is estimated as -35.6 kcal/mol for CB7• NRH^+ complex and -7.5 kcal/mol for β -CD•NR complex.

Fig. 8. Energy-optimized structures of SCX4• NRH^+ (A); SCX6• NRH^+ (B); CB7• NRH^+ (C) and β -CD•NR (D) complexes. Reproduced from Ref. 32 by permission of The Royal Society of Chemistry.

Supramolecular pK_a tuning in CB7•NR complex: Salt-induced guest relocation

The non-covalent binding interactions in host-guest complexes are weak and reversible in nature which leads to a dynamic equilibrium between the guest and the complex^{32,54}. Depending upon the binding affinity of host towards the guest, one can tune the

complexation or decomplexation/equilibrium and the associated properties, fluorescence changes, pK_a shift, etc. by using different external stimuli such as competitive binders, light, temperature, pH, etc.^{11,12,16,17,24–26,45,55–58} having established the feasibility of a pK_a shift, and the advantages of a metal ion-induced equilibrium control, the effect of metal ion on the large pK_a shift in the protolytic equilibrium of CB7•NR complex for a possible controlled guest release, with an aim to demonstrate its usefulness in a biological context, in the presence of a protein. Specifically, it is known that cations bind competitively to the portals of cucurbiturils, which can cause a displacement of the included guest, particularly when its binding is driven by the Coulombic interactions with the portals, i.e. when the guest is positively charged (protonated form). The variation of the ionic strength of the medium by addition of NaCl, therefore, allows a tuning of the pK_a value of the CB7•NR complex down to the value of the uncomplexed dye. Such a ‘supramolecular tuning’ of the pK_a value of neutral red (between 6.8–8.8) has immediate relevance for biological applications. In the presence of divalent metal ions, i.e. Ca^{2+} , a sharper decrease in the pK_a value for CB7•NR complex was observed than in the presence of the monovalent alkali ions¹¹. Presumably Ca^{2+} has, on purely electrostatic grounds, a higher binding affinity towards the CB7 portals, such that the binding constant of the CB7•NRH⁺ complex decreases more readily with added Ca^{2+} .

Extending the methodology of pK_a tuning by a macrocyclic host and salt, the applicability of this method in a biological environment has been evaluated, where the unprotonated dye would tend to be non-covalently bound to a protein. With BSA protein, its binding with neutral red can be readily followed through the changes in the absorption and fluorescence characteristics. The fluorescence titrations established that BSA shows indeed an about one order of magnitude higher affinity for NR over the NRH⁺. In the presence of BSA, the pK_a of the dye was estimated as 6.3 which could again be shifted by

Fig. 9. pH titration of the absorbance ($\lambda_{\text{mon}} = 535 \text{ nm}$) of neutral red ($3 \mu\text{M}$) in the presence of $150 \mu\text{M}$ BSA (1) in the absence of CB7 and NaCl, and (2–4) in the presence of CB7 ($50 \mu\text{M}$) with $[\text{NaCl}]/\text{M}$: (2) 0.1, (3) 0.05 and (4) 0. Inset: Normalized absorption spectra of neutral red in different environments at pH 7.5: (1) 11, (2) CB7, (3) CB7-BSA and (4) CB7-BSA-NaCl. Reproduced from Ref. 11 by permission of The Royal Society of Chemistry.

2 units, i.e. to 8.3 upon addition of CB7¹¹. This shift corresponds to the relocation of the dye in the forward direction, from BSA to CB7, where the protonated dye is more tightly bound. Following the salt-induced tuning method, the pK_a value of the dye could be further tuned by addition of a salt to the CB7•NRH⁺•BSA ternary-system¹¹. The pK_a curves generated at different salt concentrations confirm a tunability essentially over the entire range, from 8.3 to 6.3 (Fig. 9)¹¹. This shift corresponds to the relocation of the dye in the backward direction, from CB7 to BSA, where the neutral dye is more tightly bound. The net effect of the addition of metal salt is illustrated by the vertical arrow in Fig. 9, which illustrate show the addition of salt – at a constant pH near 7.5 – converts the protonated (CB7-complexed) form (top curve) into the unprotonated (BSA-complexed) form. This guest relocation is further confirmed by the absorption spectra (inset of Fig. 9)¹¹, whose maxima shifted upon addition of NaCl, from *ca.* 526 nm (characteristic for the protonated form included in CB7) to 450 nm (characteristic for the neutral form in BSA). The net effect of the salt-induced transfer of NR from CB7 to BSA is visualized in Scheme 2.

Scheme 2. Schematic representation of the salt-induced transfer of a dye from CB7 to BSA near neutral pH. Reproduced from Ref. 11 by permission of The Royal Society of Chemistry.

Moreover, since the stability and activity of drugs depend on their protonation state, the macromolecular encapsulation into CB7 could provide an interesting tool to improve drug stability through a host-assisted guest protonation. The addition of salts could then provide a simple stimulus for the controlled release of the potential drug, as well as for its activation owing to the accompanying deprotonation. Recently, Day *et al.* have examined the toxicity of CB7 and CB8 from *in vitro* studies on cell cultures and the bioadaptability of CB7/CB8 by *in vivo* studies on mice⁵⁹. Intravenous administration of CB7 showed a maximum tolerated dosage of 250 mg kg⁻¹, while oral administration of a CB7/CB8 mixture showed a tolerance of up to 600 mg kg⁻¹. The sufficiently low toxicity of CB7/CB8, their strong ability to bind various guest molecules and the guest relocation methodology established here will be interesting to explore further, especially since drug delivery appli-

cations of CB7/CB8 are presently under investigation.

Effect of metal ion on the acidity constant of SCX6-neutral red

p-Sulfonatocalixarenes, being a cationic receptor, has moderate affinity for different metal ions viz. Na⁺ (85 M⁻¹), Ca²⁺ (3820 M⁻¹), K⁺ (115 M⁻¹)⁶⁰. As discussed earlier, the addition of metal ion is then expected to lower the effective binding constants of the prototropic forms of neutral red through competitive binding and thereby shifting their effective pK_a values in the direction of the value of the uncomplexed dye. Herein, we have taken advantage of this relative binding affinity to tune pK_a of the complex close to the value of the uncomplexed dye. To achieve this tunability and calculate the pK_a shift we have carried out spectrophotometric pH titration of the dye in the presence of 1 mM SCX6/SCX4 and optimum concentration of Ca²⁺/Na⁺ ions with respect to pH.

Fig. 10 represents the pK_a titration curves of SCX complexed neutral red at varying Ca²⁺/Na⁺ ion concentrations³². The addition of Ca²⁺/Na⁺ ions to the SCX-NRH⁺ complex created competition of NRH⁺ and Ca²⁺/Na⁺ for the SCX which is confirmed by the absorption and fluorescence spectral data wherein gradual addition of Ca²⁺ and Na⁺ ions to the res-

Fig. 10. (A) pH Titration curve plotted from the absorbance at 535 nm for neutral red ($\sim 3 \mu\text{M}$), (1) in the absence of SCX6 and Ca²⁺ ion and (2–4) in the presence of SCX6 (1 mM) with [CaCl₂]/M: (2) 0.5, (3) 0.05 and (4) 0. (B) pH Titration curve plotted from the absorbance at 535 nm for neutral red ($\sim 5 \mu\text{M}$), (1) in the absence of SCX4 and Na⁺ ion and (2–4) in the presence of SCX4 (1 mM) with [NaCl]/M: (2) 0.2, (3) 0.05 and (4) 0. Reproduced from Ref. 32 by permission of The Royal Society of Chemistry.

pective SCX6:NRH⁺ and SCX4:NRH⁺ solutions at pH 5 resulted in regeneration of the absorption and fluorescence spectra of NRH⁺ (Fig. 11). The pK_a curves generated for the SCX6:NR system on increasing the salt concentration gradually shifted towards that of the free dye (Fig. 10)³². Thus the pH dependent titration of SCX6:NR in the presence of 50 mM Ca²⁺ ion shifted the pK_a value from 8.8 to 8, while 500 mM Ca²⁺ tuned the pK_a value to 7.2. Similarly, 50 mM and 200 mM Na⁺ ions shifted the pK_a value of SCX4:NR from 8.5 to 7.9 and 7.4, respectively (Fig. 10B)³². The gradual decrease in the pK_a value for the SCX:NR complex on addition of Ca²⁺/Na⁺ therefore provides not only a simple and convenient method to tune the pK_a over a large range of ~2 units, but also to reduce its affinity to SCX and thereby to affect its release from the complex.

Comparison of different host interactions on the physicochemical properties of neutral red

In order to understand the characteristic and distinct response of neutral red towards different macrocyclic hosts such as CB7, β-CD and SCX6 hosts having similar cavity size, we have compared the photophysical properties of neutral red in the presence of host molecules^{32,38,39}. Besides having a hydrophobic cavity, CB7, SCX6 and β-CD, possess

fundamentally different topologies at the upper and lower rim. CB7 is highly symmetrical with two equivalent electron rich carbonyl rims, which confers cation binding properties with cationic dyes, surfactants⁶¹, metal ions^{11,17,62}, metal nanoparticles^{63,64}, aminoacids⁶⁵, proteins¹⁸, etc., while the electron deficient peripheral group shows interaction towards polyanions such as poly-oxometalates³⁷. β-CD has truncated cone shape with, wider rim laced with secondary hydroxyl groups and a lower one with primary hydroxyl groups and these promote binding mainly by hydrogen bonding and hydrophobic interactions^{22,23,45}. On the other hand, the cone shaped SCX6 contains negatively charged sulfonate groups at the portals of SCX host which influence more the cationic guests through anion-cation electrostatic interaction^{24–26}. These differences account largely for the differential binding of both host molecules with neutral red. Complexation of protonated NRH⁺ form with SCX6 and CB7 is greatly preferred due to the additional ion-dipole interactions, thereby resulting in large difference in the binding constants as listed in Table 1 as well as the pronounced pK_a shift toward higher values (≥2 units), which also reflects the increased stability of the protonated dye in the complex^{32,38}. Whereas complexation by β-CD, is stronger for the neutral form ($K = 4.1 \times 10^2 \text{ M}^{-1}$), due to its hydrophilic nature and hence

Fig. 11. (A) Fluorescence spectra of NRH⁺ (1) in the absence of SCX6 and (2–8) in the presence of SCX6 (77 μM) with [CaCl₂]/mM: (2) 0.0, (3) 0.9, (4) 2.8, (5) 6.5, (6) 14.8, (7) 27.5 and (8) 63.6. (B) Fluorescence spectra of NRH⁺ (1) in the absence of SCX4 and (2–8) in the presence of SCX4 (150 μM) with [NaCl]/mM: (2) 0.0, (3) 1.85, (4) 3.7, (5) 7.4, (6) 18.5, (7) 54.7 and (8) 125.0. Insets show the corresponding absorption spectra. Reproduced from Ref. 32 by permission of The Royal Society of Chemistry.

Table 1. Binding constant values for NRH⁺ and NR with different macrocyclic hosts and the pK_a shift recorded in the respective cases. Reproduced from Ref. 32 by permission of The Royal Society of Chemistry

Hosts	Binding constant (K)/M ⁻¹		ΔpK _a
	NRH ⁺	NR	
SCX6	(3.8±0.5)×10 ⁵	(4.8±0.5)×10 ³	2.3
SCX4	(1.3±0.1)×10 ⁴	(6.1±0.5)×10 ³	2.0
CB7	(6.0±1.0)×10 ⁵	(6.5±1.0)×10 ³	2.0
β-CD	-	(4.1±0.5)×10 ²	-0.7

has a better water solubility and a lower tendency to be immersed in a hydrophobic environment³⁹. The reduced binding of the protonated form accounts similarly for the sizable pK_a shift toward lower values (from 6.8 to 6.1)³⁹, reflecting a lower stability of the protonated form in its β-CD complex. Since CB7 and SCX hosts are cation receptors, metal ion induced guest release from the host cavity is achieved through competitive interaction^{11,26,32}. Interestingly the fluorescence intensity of both the forms gets enhanced in the presence of CB7 and β-CD due to the restriction in the vibrational and rotational motions of the N(CH₃)₂ group of the dye by confinement or less polar microenvironment inside the CB7/β-CD cavities, which effectively prevents the radiationless deactivation pathways of the excited molecule^{38,39}. On the other hand, the substantial decrease in the emission intensity in the presence of SCX6/SCX4 host has been attributed to the electron transfer from the phenolic hydroxyl groups to the NRH⁺ form³². Similar kinds of pK_a changes in NRH⁺ were observed in the presence of a higher homologue of CB7 i.e. cucurbit[8]uril (CB8)^{13,56,66-68}, but the fluorescence intensity was quenched in the presence of CB8 due to the formation of dimer^{1,13}. The differential behavior of different macrocycles towards neutral red can be attributed to the different chemical constituents, variation in the cavity sizes and dissimilar portal interactions. While an axial inclusion through the cavity is common for CB7/CB8 and β-CD macrocycles, with SCXs the NRH⁺ dye preferred a portal stacking interaction as revealed in the geometry optimization studies (Fig. 8). This explains the striking differences in the photophysical attributes of SCXs-NR system and with the aid of the metal

ion induced fluorescence regeneration and pK_a shift, the photophysical properties neutral red can be conveniently modulated by the host cavities and external stimuli.

Conclusions

This article provides an account of the photophysical and protolytic changes in the cationic (NRH⁺) and neutral (NR) forms of the neutral red dye on interaction with cucurbit[7]uril, *p*-sulfonatocalix[4/6]arene (SCX4/6) and β-cyclodextrin macrocycles. The fluorescence intensity of both NRH⁺ and NR gets quenched upon addition of SCX4/6, whereas the fluorescence intensity increases in the presence of β-CD and CB7. All the photophysical changes confirm inclusion complex formation between the host and dye, however, the protonated form shows stronger interaction towards SCX and CB7 than the neutral form. The large upward pK_a shift (≥2 units) in the dye upon complexation also reflects the strong affinity of SCX and CB7 to the protonated form, which is stabilized in the complex by ion-ion interactions with the sulfonato groups of SCX and ion-dipole interaction with the carbonyl portals of CB7. Distinctly, neutral red dye gets stacked on to the -SO₃⁻ portals of the SCXs bringing out emission quenching through a static interaction and is in contrast to the axial inclusion documented in case of the CB7 and the β-CD. The modulation in the photophysical properties of both the forms of neutral red upon formation of inclusion complexes with macrocyclic hosts are of great current interest and since the release and activity of the desired protolytic form of the dye/drugs can be controlled by regulating the protolytic equilibrium, the reported macro-molecular encapsulation and release, fluorescence regeneration and metal ion induced pK_a tuning etc. discussed here find relevance to the host-guest based drug delivery systems, photodynamic therapy, catalysis, and *off-on* sensor applications.

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